

Application of Management Matrix as Predictor of Principal's Managerial Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the application of management matrix as predictor of principals' management effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State. The descriptive research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of 5,246 teachers of public secondary schools in the study area while the sampling size which was randomly chosen comprised 1,246 teachers. The instrument for the study was a 10 item structured questionnaire that consisted of two clusters. Cluster A dealt with the extent of the application of management matrix by principals of schools while cluster B was concerned with the factors that affect the application of management matrix in public secondary schools in the study area. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy one from the Department of Education Foundations. All in the Faculty of Education. The reliability of the instrument was obtained through Cronback Alpha with cluster A weighing 0.76 and cluster B weighing 0.84, all having a weighted average of 0.80 which was considered high enough for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypotheses were rejected when the calculated p-value was less than 0.05 level of significance while it was accepted when the calculated p-value was higher than the 0.05 level of significance. The finding of the study showed among others that most principals are ignorant of the application of management matrix, as such their managerial effectiveness is not enhanced. It was therefore recommended that the Ministry of Education in the study area should expose the principals or heads of schools to the rudiments and application of management matrix.

Keywords: *Management, Matrix, Predictor, Effectiveness.*

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Introduction

Management matrix can be used to explain the structures of operation or work that are directed

or handled by one person or worker. It describes a situation where a superordinate is assigned with two or more lines of duties. Matrix itself is an arrangement of numbers, columns or lines

with the intention of treating them as a simple quantity or volume. In the political setting, matrix can be described as the arrangement of ideas or events emerging from diverse sources into a holistic ideology in order to structure the political space or society organically (Ikheloa, 2018). This structuring can take the form of simulation of lines or structures of duties. The essence however is to ensure that lines of duties are given or treated with the highest competence that would give or produce the best quality products or services required by stakeholders.

This in another language would involve streamlining economic policies, health policies, education policies and even agricultural policies to synergize efforts being made for optimum productivity. The individual selected to handle this matrix is so resourceful enough to perform or deliver without changing or alternating the job design. Esse (2020) stated that such a worker should be a superordinate proven with a good track record of optimum performance and an unequivocal record of satisfactory delivery.

In the education sector, management matrix has been very operational. It involves a teacher reporting to two or more bosses. This is where a Mathematics teacher is reporting to his unit head, his head of department, his sectional head and even his principal. Idris (2021) opined that the operation or application of management matrix in this form is minimal and not noticed because according to him it is seen as a normal line of duties within the chain of command. Arauloi (2018) stated that in a wider sense, management matrix involves asking a Physics teacher for instance to consult with a Mathematics teacher periodically for problems in the teaching of his subjects that the Mathematics teacher could be helpful. In a more clearer language, it is a situation where a superordinate is made to supervise two or more number of staff in and outside his department.

Management matrix is not the same as collaborative teaching. The former has to do with allowing a teacher to consult his senior colleagues within and outside his department who are experienced in his subject area while the latter involves teachers in the same department synergizing to get the work done because of the

unit areas of specialization (Obanor, 2017). The need for the application of management matrix by principals or heads of schools cannot be over emphasized. Firstly, it makes for proficiency in teaching as it makes principals of schools to place teachers in the areas they are best suited for. This creates room for the use of experts who would always bring their high degree of cognitiveness in their various fields to bear on teaching and learning (Mayebi, 2023).

Management matrix if applied by heads of schools enhances intra-collegiate synergy. In other words, it helps to build a strong work relationship between departments and sections of the school. Borderline structures that create barricades between units, departments and sections are automatically collapsed and this makes for work cohesion within a school thereby enhancing principals' managerial effectiveness (Linus, 2023).

It also makes for principals' accessibility to information especially as it relates to teachers' job performance proficiency index. This is because it makes for different supervisors filing reports to the principal on the delivery capacity of teachers within and outside the departments. Principals are therefore provided with robust records that are needed for teachers' job performance appraisal at the end of the school term or session (Uwakabiri, 2022).

Principals application of management matrix could be premised on a lot of indices. The principal concerned must be resourceful enough to see the concept as a worthwhile venture. In other words, the principal must believe that the application of management matrix would deepen his job and make for his managerial effectiveness. Ikheloa (2012) added that the head of school concerned must have been the type that can think out of the box. This according to him is because the application of management matrix is not common in secondary schools in the study area.

Another component of management matrix is that there must be qualified and experienced teachers across the various departments and sections that are willing to participate in such horizontal work setting. Funtua (2020) added that the concept of management matrix can be

applied in big secondary schools where there are many teachers with capacity and quality delivery. The challenge however is that such teachers are rare in the school system.

Management matrix improves principals managerial effectiveness because in addition to the above inputs, it enriches the principal's jobs. The application widens the principal's thought dialectics and makes him have a firm grip of both human and material resources under his control. Idris (2021) is of the opinion that it makes principals dialectical in reasoning and widens their consultation space which are needed for the flexibility and malleability which the headship and his management job demand.

The only challenge in the application of management matrix is that it slows down decision making especially as it relates to teacher's job evaluation or appraisal. Funtua (2020) however dismissed such argument as according to him, such delay could be necessary if it will help to reduce mistakes in decision making and implementation.

Typologically, management matrix requires some technicalities in its application. This is because it involves latent reasoning which in most cases is not common among managers. In addition, it requires a high level of managerial craftsmanship which is made possible by depth and insightfulness. This according to Esse (2020) is a very scarce ingredient among managers of the 21st century who depend on technology to make decisions. Succinctly however, the extent of the application of management matrix is a measure of the managerial effectiveness of the principal of a public secondary school, especially in the study area.

Statement of the Problem

The idea of management matrix is about a worker reporting or taking instructions from two or three superordinates. In the school system, this work structure is not always there except may be in big schools. The need for management matrix in the school system cannot be over-stretched. Firstly, it helps to reduce or minimize the chances of making mistakes in decision making. This results in minimal risk of failure. As two good heads are better than one,

management matrix makes for robust ideas being injected into work, thus an enlarged work technology is ensured leading to quality work performance and result. The agitation against management matrix is that it leads to delay in the process of consultation and work performance. However, this argument is debunked on the ground that it is better work is delayed than an organization or a school facing the risk of failure due to hasty decisions.

In spite of the above discussed gains of management matrix, it does appear that job performance and their associated results do not represent inputs made into the school system. In addition to this situation, there is the dearth of empirical research on the subject of the study. It is against this back ground that this study investigated the application of management matrix as determinant of principals' managerial effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo State.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent does the application of management matrix improve principals' managerial effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo state?
2. What are the factors that mitigate the application of management matrix in public secondary schools in Imo State?

Hypotheses

The study is aided with the following hypotheses:

1. The application of management matrix does not improve principals' managerial effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo state.
2. There are no factors mitigating the application of management matrix in public secondary schools in Imo state.

Method

The study investigated the application of management matrix as predictor of principals' management effectiveness in public secondary

schools in Imo State. The descriptive research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of 5,246 teachers of public secondary schools in the study area while the sampling size which was randomly chosen comprised 1,246 teachers. The instrument for the study was a 10 item structured questionnaire that consisted of two clusters. Cluster A dealt with the extent of the application of management matrix by principals of schools while cluster B was concerned with the factors that affect the application of management matrix in public secondary schools in the study area. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy one from the Department of Education Foundations. All in the Faculty of Education. The reliability of the instrument was obtained through Cronback

Alpha with cluster A weighing 0.76 and cluster B weighing 0.84, all having a weighted average of 0.80 which was considered high enough for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypotheses were rejected when the calculated p-value was less than 0.05 level of significance while it was accepted when the calculated p-value was higher than the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does the application of management matrix improve principals' managerial effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo state?

Table 1. Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent to which Application of Management Matrix Improve Principals' Managerial Effectiveness

S/N	To what extent do Principals:	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Application of management matrix enhances principals' managerial effectiveness	2.70	.76	HE
2.	It allows teachers to handle their areas of specialization	2.49	.73	LE
3.	It makes for competence in the teaching of subjects	2.50	.75	HE
4.	It makes for innovative teaching	2.75	.74	HE
5.	It helps principals to coordinate their teaching and learning effectively	2.50	.70	HE
Cluster Mean		2.58	0.72	HE

The analysis displayed in Table 1 indicates the mean ratings of respondents on the extent to which the application of management matrix improves principals' managerial effectiveness. The cluster mean of 2.58 and standard deviation of 0.72 indicate that Principals to a high extent revealed that application of management matrix

improve principals' managerial effectiveness in public secondary schools in Imo state.

Research Question 2: What are the factors that affect the application of management matrix in public secondary schools in Imo State?

Table 2. Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Factors that Affect the Application of Management Matrix

S/N	To what extent do Principals:	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	There are factors that affect the application of management matrix.	2.57	.85	Agree
2.	Ignorance on the part of the principal can hinder the application.	2.84	.75	Agree
3.	The fact that it causes delay in teaching and learning is equally a problem.	2.66	.82	Agree
4.	Not having teachers in their right number can affect the application of management matrix.	2.54	.79	Agree
5.	If well-coordinated, management matrix can cause an improvement in principals' managerial effectiveness.	2.58	.97	Agree

Table 2 shows the mean ratings of respondents on the factors that affect the application of management matrix in public secondary schools in Imo State. The respondents agreed that the five listed factors affect the application of management matrix in public secondary schools in Imo State. Their mean ratings ranged from 2.57 to 2.84.

Discussion

Table 1 showed that the respondents were in agreement that principals' use of management matrix helps to enhance their managerial effectiveness. This presupposes that there is a significant relationship between the application of management matrix and principals' capacity to synergize with other relevant bodies beyond the borders of their schools. Pulling human resources together from different sections in an organization or school represents a normative pattern of team collaboration.

Such initiative as stated above helps to extract latent ideas and novel ways of achieving targets. This is in agreement with Esse (2020) who stressed that matrix management is the result of creative thinking. It is this submission that the respondents accepted or agreed with.

Table 2 raised issues on the factors that affect the application of management matrix by principals in the study area. The respondents agreed that ignorance, delay, inadequate number of teachers and other factors as contained in the table inhibit the application of management matrix by principals of secondary schools in Imo State. The mean ratings of which ranged from 2.57 to 2.84 is the statistical expression of the respondents indicating that they approved or agreed that they are factors affecting the application of management matrix in schools.

Conclusion

In view of the above findings, it is empirically proved that application of management matrix will improve the effectiveness of principals' managerial skills and competencies. It is therefore seen that there are factors that impair the application of management matrix by principals of secondary schools in the study area.

Recommendations

The study investigated the application of management matrix by principals of secondary schools to enhance their managerial effectiveness in the study area. From the findings of the study and the conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

1. Educational managers, especially in the ministry should make the application of management matrix popular among principals of secondary schools in the study area.
2. Principals of secondary schools should synergize among themselves on the application of management matrix through seminars and workshops.
3. The issue of delay in the application of management matrix by school heads could be resolved through planning.

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